

Dataset from Digitised EU Recipe Collections and IP Issues

Míriam Herrero-Valea, Fernando Cucchiatti, and Roger González. March 31, 2025.
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AUTHOR(S)	Míriam Herrero-Valea, Fernando Cucchietti, Roger González
CONTRIBUTOR(S)	Enrico Bonadio, José Camarena López, Jeffrey Newman
REVIEWER(S)	Joan Ribas Serra, Jeffrey Newman, Andrea Borghini, Augusto Esteves
APPROVER	H. Rosi Song

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Abbreviations and acronyms

TERM	DEFINITION	TERM	DEFINITION
D[No.]	Deliverable [No.]	NLP	Natural Language Processing
EC	European Commission	T[No.]	Task [No.]
LLM	Large Language Model	TDM	Text and Data Mining
NER	Named Entity Recognition	WP[No.]	Work Package [No.]

Consortium

ROLE	NAME	SHORT NAME	COUNTRY
Coordinator	University of Durham	UDUR	UK
Partner	Atlantic Technological University	ATU	Ireland
Partner	Barcelona Supercomputing Center	BSC	Spain
Partner	City, University of London	CITY	UK
Partner	Fundació Alícia	FA	Spain
Partner	Institut LYFE	LYFE	France
Partner	Instituto Superior Técnico	IST	Portugal
Partner	Roskilde University	RUC	Denmark
Partner	University College Cork	UCC	Ireland
Partner	University of Alicante	UA	Spain
Partner	University of Gastronomic Sciences of Pollenzo	UNISG	Italy
Partner	University of Milan	UMIL	Italy
Partner	University of Toronto	UoT	Canada

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Executive Summary

This précis presents Deliverable 3.3, a dataset of cooking recipes from European regions, spanning from the Roman Empire to the present day.

The dataset was compiled with the goal of understanding the evolution of culinary techniques, tastes, and trends across both spatial and temporal dimensions within the European continent, as well as their connections with external influences, such as Arab cuisine.

Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), with contributions from Fundació Alícia (FA), Durham University (UDUR), and University of Toronto (UoT), compiled the dataset and City, University of London (CITY) provided advisement on IP issues for WP3: INGREDIENTS. Additional reviews were provided by University of Milan (UMIL), University of Toronto (UoT) and Instituto Superior Técnico (IST).

1 Introduction

RELISH (Reframing European gastronomy Legacy through Innovation, Sustainability and Heritage) is a three-year Horizon Europe-funded project that offers a pathway to put into practice culinary recipes and food culture as cultural and digital tools to strengthen a crucial aspect of EU's common cultural heritage. Through an innovative and systematic approach to the understanding and use of traditional EU recipes via digital and AI-powered technology, it embarks on the production of a visual and verbal food storytelling web platform that aims to mediate social cohesion, reinforce EU cultural heritage transmission both at home and abroad through education and public engagement, while addressing sustainable practices in the home kitchen and the EU hospitality sector.

BSC and FA completed the following D3.3 to meet one of WP3's objectives:

- To collect data on digitised traditional EU recipes and sustainability impact of recipes to support the development of the digital tool for recipe visualisation of the project

1.1 Description of the document

This deliverable précis presents the compilation and development of a dataset of cooking recipes from European regions, spanning from the Roman Empire to the

present day. All recipes were obtained from openly available digitised cookbooks in several living and dead languages, translated into modern English, normalised, and processed to extract their key elements using natural language processing (NLP) techniques.

The dataset was compiled with the goal of understanding the evolution of culinary techniques, tastes, and trends across both spatial and temporal dimensions within the European continent, as well as their connections with external influences, such as Arab cuisine.

While extant digitised recipe corpora have featured searchability and comparability, this RELISH dataset offers novel systematic and visualisation capacities. It also integrates the development of new tools, such as NLP techniques, and categories for search and analysis.

This précis outlines steps for accessing data, creating and compiling the dataset, processing methods, and a brief commentary on the availability of historical culinary recipe data in Europe.

2 Dataset Description

The dataset comprises **6,024 recipes** from multiple open sources (Table 1). A significant proportion of these recipes originates from a previous related project, CoReMA.¹ The remaining recipes were sourced from Project Gutenberg, the University of Giessen Historical Cookbooks collection, Fundació Alícia (FA), and other publicly available archives. The distribution of recipes per source is illustrated in **Figure 1**.

¹ <https://gams.uni-graz.at/context:corema>

Figure 1: Distribution of recipes by source.

2.1 Dataset identification

Digitised and open-source European historical recipe datasets were initially sourced from RELISH partners and networks, including CoReMa, The Sifter, and Fundació Alícia (FA). Limitations arose in finalising dataset transfer from one UDUR partner due to extenuating circumstances.

To augment the dataset and contextualise historical recipe collection availability, UoT and UDUR conducted a supplementary search, focussing on identifying or procuring the following:

- Open-source datasets (with relevant metadata) interoperable with BSC's database
- OCRred or scrapable historical recipe and cookbook corpora
- Digitisation prevalence and geographic availability in European contexts of historical (ancient, medieval, early modern) recipe or cookbook corpora

- Limitations and/or opportunities for harnessing material and digital recipe corpora for future RELISH exploitation

The search scope was limited to corpora, collections, and datasets that featured European culinary recipes. Medicinal and artisan recipes (*e.g.*, dyes, inks) were excluded.

2.1.1 Dataset search

Using Google Search, UoT and UDUR developed search chains and documentation for primarily identifying useful regional or national historical recipe corpora.

Relevant but not yet useful corpora or collections and secondary discussions were also tracked to contextualise developments in or existence of institutional and/or commercial projects digitising and utilising historical recipe corpora for research, hobbyist networks, and/or services and applications.

UoT and UDUR developed two types of search chains: specific and broad.

Specific search chain formula:

([name of country or region]) AND (recipe OR recipes) AND (medieval OR historical OR early-modern OR cultural) AND (database OR repository OR corpora OR json OR xml OR archive)

To catch any outliers to relevant resources, we also conducted a broad search query for “digitised historical recipes and/or collections.”

Searches were first conducted in English. Using AI translation, UoT also supplemented searches with corresponding language search chains.

Search chains for geographic and historical regions or places included current and extant nomenclature. For example, one search chain would include (Turkey OR Türkiye OR Byzantine OR Byzantium OR Ottoman). This generated greater variety of relevant results.

Where possible, UoT and UDUR also used non-exhaustively and based on familiarity:

- Exonyms and endonyms for place names, *e.g.*, (Welsh OR Wales OR Cymru);
- Historically relevant city-state or regional nomenclature, *e.g.*, (Florentine OR Florence OR Fiorentino OR Firenze); and

- Ethnonyms or autonyms, *e.g.*, (Ireland OR Irish OR Celtic OR Gaelic).

URLs to useful or relevant materials were uploaded to the tracking sheet and sent to BSC for review.

2.1.2 Search results

Useful results were integrated into the dataset. The search process ultimately highlighted the difficulties and limitations in accessing non-licensed or Public Domain digitised recipe corpora and datasets.

Additional sources for future review, such as OCRed or to-be-ORCed open source manuscripts, archival collections, and individual academic or hobbyist databases, were tracked and shared with relevant partners.

3 Data Collection Methodology

Data were collected from several publicly available online sources. These are listed in **Table 1**, together with metadata on the corresponding books, their geographical and temporal origin, and their original language.

Table 1: Metadata of source manuscripts and cookbooks.

TITLE	YEAR	LOCATION	SOURCE	LANGUAGE
De Re Coquinaria (Apicius)	1 st c.	Roman Empire	Project Gutenberg	English
CoReMA Manuscript M11	1350	Würzburg, Bavaria	CoReMA	Old German
CoReMA Manuscript W1	1400	Vienna, Austria	CoReMA	Old German
CoReMA Manuscript B5	1425	Beßlich, Rhineland	CoReMA	Old German
CoReMA Manuscript Ds1	1425	Central Germany	CoReMA	Old German
CoReMA Manuscript Br1	1435	Bavaria, Germany	CoReMA	Old German
CoReMA Manuscript Er1	1441	Heilsbronn, Bavaria	CoReMA	Old German
CoReMA Manuscript B1	1445	Mainz, Germany	CoReMA	Old German
CoReMA Manuscript B2	1450	Öttingen, Germany	CoReMA	Old German

TITLE	YEAR	LOCATION	SOURCE	LANGUAGE
CoReMA Manuscript B4	1450	Bavaria, Germany	CoReMA	Old German
CoReMA Manuscript W4	1451	Bavaria, Germany	CoReMA	Old German
CoReMA Manuscript Bs1	1460	Bavaria-Alemannic region	CoReMA	Old German
CoReMA Manuscript Db1	1470	Bavaria, Germany	CoReMA	Old German
CoReMA Manuscript B6	1475	Bavaria, Germany	CoReMA	Old German
CoReMA Manuscript Gr1	1475	Germany	CoReMA	Old German
CoReMA Manuscript So1	1487	Upper Germany	CoReMA	Old German
CoReMA Manuscript B3	1497	Alemannic region	CoReMA	Old German
CoReMA Manuscript Bs2	1500	East Franconia-Bavaria	CoReMA	Old German
CoReMA Manuscript K1	1500	West Central Germany	CoReMA	Old German
CoReMA Manuscript Pa1	1500	Bavaria, Germany	CoReMA	Old German
CoReMA Manuscript Wo8	1625	Germany	CoReMA	Old German
Cuina Catalana	2025	Catalonia, Spain	cuinacatalana.eu	Catalan
A Miscellany of Recipes	1400	England	Project Gutenberg	English
Historische Esskultur	2020	Austria	historische-esskultur.at	German
Liber de Coquina / Tractatus	1300	France / Italy	Univ. of Giessen	Latin
Viandier (Ms Sion S 108)	1350	Sion, Switzerland	Univ. of Giessen	Old French
Libro de arte coquinaria	1465	Rome, Italy	Univ. of Giessen	Italian
Libro della cocina	1400	Florence, Italy	Univ. of Giessen	Italian
Liber de coquina	1350	Naples, Italy	Univ. of Giessen	Latin
Le viandier pour appareiller...	1485	Paris, France	Univ. of Giessen	Middle French
Epistola de caseis et operibus lactariis	1556	Chur, Switzerland	Univ. of Giessen	Latin
Liber cure cocorum	1430	Dortmund, Germany	Univ. of Giessen	Middle Low German
Tractatus de modo preparandi...	1350	Avignon, France	Univ. of Giessen	Latin

TITLE	YEAR	LOCATION	SOURCE	LANGUAGE
Ouverture de Cuisine	1604	Liège, Belgium	Univ. of Giessen	French
A new booke of Cookerie	1615	London, England	Univ. of Giessen	Early Modern English
A Proper newe Booke of Cokerye	1550	Oxford, England	Univ. of Giessen	Early Modern English
Libre de totes maneres de confits	1450	Barcelona, Spain	Univ. of Giessen	Catalan
Viandier, Manuscrit du Vatican	1350	Paris, France	Univ. of Giessen	Old French
Enseignements	1300	Paris, France	Univ. of Giessen	Old French
Keukenboek	1450	Bruges, Belgium	Univ. of Giessen	Middle Dutch
Harpestreng Cookbook (Codex K)	1250	Copenhagen, Denmark	Univ. of Giessen	Old Danish
Libro di cucina / Libro per cuoco	1400	Venice, Italy	Univ. of Giessen	Venetian/ Italian
L'art de la cuina De re coquinaria	1300	Barcelona, Spain	Fundació Alícia	Catalan
Llibre de Sent Soví	1350	Barcelona, Spain	Fundació Alícia	Catalan
Llibre d'aparellar de menjar	1400	Barcelona, Spain	Fundació Alícia	Catalan
Llibre de totes maneres de potatges	1450	Barcelona, Spain	Fundació Alícia	Catalan
Llibre del coc	1380	Barcelona, Spain	Fundació Alícia	Catalan
Llibre de cuina d'Escaladei	1600	Barcelona, Spain	Fundació Alícia	Catalan
Llibre molt apte per al govern...	1800	Barcelona, Spain	Fundació Alícia	Catalan
Avisos i instruccions per lo principiant cuiner	1750	Barcelona, Spain	Fundació Alícia	Catalan
Art de la cuina	1600	Barcelona, Spain	Fundació Alícia	Catalan
La cuina dels carmelites descalços	1700	Barcelona, Spain	Fundació Alícia	Catalan
Modo de cuinar a la Mallorquina	1800	Palma de Mallorca	Fundació Alícia	Catalan
Receptari Caules	1600	Barcelona, Spain	Fundació Alícia	Catalan
La Cuynera Catalana	1850	Barcelona, Spain	Fundació Alícia	Catalan

TITLE	YEAR	LOCATION	SOURCE	LANGUAGE
La teca	1900	Barcelona, Spain	Fundació Alícia	Catalan
Llibre de la cuina catalana	1950	Barcelona, Spain	Fundació Alícia	Catalan
Corpus Culinari de la Cuina Catalana	2000	Barcelona, Spain	Fundació Alícia	Catalan
Llibre del Sent Soví	1450	Barcelona, Spain	Fundació Alícia	Catalan

3.1 Pre-processing

After extraction, each book was segmented into sections, from which individual recipes were identified and isolated. The resulting pre-processed dataset thus consists of a list of recipes in their original languages.

3.2 Translation

All recipes were then translated into modern English using a publicly available large language model (LLM), deployed on the **MareNostrum 5** high-performance computing infrastructure at BSC. Specifically, the **Gemma 3–27B model** was employed with the following prompt:

You are a translator in {language}. The text below is a recipe in {language}. Take into account the culinary context. Translate it to modern English. Do not include any note, nor any comment. Just provide the translation. {text}

3.3 Entity extraction

The final processing step involved the extraction of named entities—specifically ingredients, tools, and techniques—from the translated recipes. This was achieved using a Named Entity Recognition (NER) model based on **ModernBERT-base**,² fine-tuned on the **RISec dataset**³ and subsequently applied to the full corpus. While the extraction achieves high accuracy, it is not perfect and will be refined through ongoing human validation of the labelling process.

² <https://huggingface.co/answerdotai/ModernBERT-base>

³ <https://github.com/YiweiJiang2015/RISec>

RELISH partners and volunteers have been recruited to help label and verify the dataset throughout the duration of the project.

4 Dataset Structure

The complete dataset is stored as a single JSON file containing the original recipes, their machine translations, and the extracted entities. The dataset contains 6,024 records.

5 Metadata and Variables

The dataset is structured as a list of JSON records rather than a flat tabular format. This choice reflects the variable-length, nested nature of the extracted entities — each recipe may contain a different number of ingredients, tools, and actions, each with its own list of surface-form variants — which cannot be adequately represented in a fixed-column table without significant redundancy or information loss. The specific choice of variables here attends to a rationale based on maximizing the information that can be extracted from the text by NLP techniques without external conte

FIELD	TYPE	REQUIRED	DESCRIPTION
source_id	string	yes	Unique identifier of the source from which the recipe was extracted.
title	string	yes	Title of the recipe, as it appears in the original source.
recipe_text	string	yes	Full text of the recipe, translated into modern English. Used as the primary input for NER and embedding generation.
source_year	integer null	yes	Approximate year of composition or publication of the source document.
source_place	string null	yes	Geographical origin of the source document.
source_language	string null	yes	Original language of the source document, before translation.
translation	string null	yes	Modern English version of the recipe, obtained through machine translation (GPT-4o). Null if the original was already in English.

SOURCE METADATA FIELDS

FIELD	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
source_title	string null	Full title of the source manuscript or cookbook.
source_author	string null	Author of the source document. "Anonymous" if unknown.
period	string null	Century label for the source document. One of: 6th, 13th, 14th, 15th, 16th, 17th.

ingredients – array of ingredients objects

SUB-FIELD	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
name	string	Core normalised ingredient name (e.g. wine, pepper, egg).
specific_forms	string[]	Contextual variants (e.g., black pepper, ½ teaspoon pepper, good red wine).
confidence_score	float	NER confidence (0.0–1.0).

Average per recipe: 8.9 ingredients. Total unique ingredient types: 6,621.

tools – array of cooking tool objects

SUB-FIELD	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
name	string	Core normalised tool name (e.g. pan, mortar, bowl).
specific_forms	string[]	Contextual variants (e.g., frying pan, earthenware bowl, a large mortar).
confidence_score	float	NER confidence (0.0–1.0).

Average per recipe: 1.7 tools. Total unique tool types: 1,864.

actions — array of cooking action objects

SUB-FIELD	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
verb	string	Core normalised cooking verb (e.g., bake, add, take).
specific_forms	string[]	Surface-text variants (e.g. baked, baking, add in).
confidence_score	float	NER confidence (0.0–1.0).

Average per recipe: 5.5 actions. Total unique action types: 643.

6 Data Quality and Limitations

The dataset is currently undergoing validation by members of the consortium through an open-source, dedicated frontend system called **Data Labeller**, which presents users with the original recipe alongside its translated version, with the extracted entities highlighted. Several known limitations of the processing pipeline are:

- **Language diversity:** The original texts are written in many different languages, some of which have no living speakers. This poses a significant challenge for translation quality, as semantic ranges may differ across languages and some words may lack direct equivalents in modern English.
- **Entity recognition accuracy:** Due to the inherent complexity of natural language—particularly in historical texts—the NER model occasionally fails to identify or correctly classify certain entities.

To mitigate these issues, the translation pipeline relies on the LLM’s ability to infer meaning from context, rather than pursuing literal word-for-word translation. A carefully designed prompt—shown in **section 3.2**—supplies the model with relevant context. Additionally, human validation serves as a complementary quality assurance mechanism for continuous improvement of the data processing pipeline. At this time, data validation is in progress.

7 Data Availability and Access

The processed dataset is available via Zenodo at DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19328667 (see **Annex I**). It is released to the public under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International** licence.

The dataset is distributed as a single JSON file and can be freely downloaded, reused, and redistributed in accordance with the terms of the applicable licence. Users are encouraged to cite the Zenodo record when making use of the dataset in derived works or publications.

The raw source texts, prior to translation and entity extraction, remain available at their original repositories as listed in **Table 1**. Key source collections are distributed under open licences that explicitly permit reuse: the CoReMA corpus, which accounts for a large proportion of the dataset, is released under a **CC 4.0** licence for text. Other

sources, such as Project Gutenberg, provide works in the public domain. Where individual repositories impose additional terms of use, researchers should consult the relevant source directly.

8 Legal and Ethical Considerations

The compilation of a multilingual historical recipe dataset from digitised sources raises a number of legal and ethical questions, particularly regarding copyright, database rights, and the use of content for AI-assisted processing. This section outlines the considerations that guided the design and release of the dataset.

8.1 Copyright and public domain

The vast majority of source texts in this dataset originate from historical manuscripts and cookbooks dating from the 1st century to the early modern period. These works are firmly in the public domain owing to the expiration of any applicable copyright terms. In most jurisdictions, including the EU and the United States, basic recipes consisting of ingredient lists and procedural instructions are not considered copyrightable, as they constitute functional directions rather than original literary expression.

Where more recent sources are included (20th- and 21st-century), care has been taken to draw only from openly licensed or publicly available collections. In particular, the CoReMA project—which contributes a substantial share of the medieval recipes in this dataset—publishes its transcriptions under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) licence for text, which explicitly permits copying, redistribution, and adaptation, provided that appropriate credit is given. Attribution to CoReMA and all other sources is systematically recorded in the dataset metadata via the `source_id` field.

It should be noted that copyright protection may attach to expressive elements accompanying a recipe—such as personal anecdotes, cultural commentary, or narrative descriptions—even when the underlying list of ingredients and steps is not protectable. The translation and entity-extraction pipeline used in this project processes the functional content of recipes and does not reproduce such expressive elements in the final dataset.

8.2 Database rights

Under the EU Database Directive (96/9/EC), *sui generis* database rights protect the substantial investment made in obtaining, verifying, or presenting the contents of a database. Several of the source collections used in this project—notably CoReMA—represent significant curatorial and scholarly effort.

In the case of CoReMA, the adoption of a CC BY 4.0 licence for its textual content mitigates database rights concerns, as the licence grants explicit permission to extract and reuse the material provided that attribution is given. For other source collections, the extraction of recipes was carried out in accordance with applicable text and data mining (TDM) provisions under the EU Digital Single Market Directive (2019/790), which permits the reproduction and extraction of lawfully accessible content for the purposes of scientific research.

8.3 Text and data mining provisions

The dataset was compiled and processed within the framework of a scientific research project. The EU TDM exception (Article 3 of Directive 2019/790) permits research organisations and cultural heritage institutions to carry out text and data mining on lawfully accessible works for scientific research purposes. The use of a large language model for translation and a NER model for entity extraction falls within the scope of this exception, as these processes constitute computational analysis of textual data for research purposes.

It is worth noting that the normative landscape surrounding the use of copyrighted content for AI training remains unsettled, with ongoing litigation and divergent judicial interpretations across jurisdictions. This dataset has been compiled in good faith under current provisions, and its terms of use will be updated as the legal framework evolves.

8.4 Ethical considerations

Beyond legal compliance, this project is guided by a commitment to cultural respect and scholarly integrity. Historical recipes are cultural artefacts that reflect the traditions, knowledge, and creativity of the communities that produced them. The dataset has been assembled with the aim of preserving and making accessible this culinary heritage, not of displacing or diminishing the original sources.

All source materials are fully attributed in the dataset metadata, and users are encouraged to engage with the original texts and their cultural contexts. The project team is committed to transparent documentation of its methodology, including the limitations of machine translation and automated entity extraction, so that downstream users can make informed assessments of data quality and fitness for purpose.

9 Potential Impact

Overall, initial access to partner collections and networks provided reliable and expedient recipe data. However, European open-source historical recipe datasets are highly limited and/or fragmented, which suggests **significant opportunities** for extraction and centralisation.

RELISH has identified the need for more funding/resources to support further European historical recipe data and database extraction and centralisation.

Identifying national and institutional libraries and archives with digitised open-source collections may be useful for conducting searches for OCRed or OCR-able recipe corpora not currently available or hosted in transnational repositories (*e.g.*, Project Gutenberg, Archive.org).

10 Conclusions

This document has presented the European Historical Culinary Recipes Dataset, a curated collection of 6,024 recipes spanning from the 1st-century Roman Empire to the present day. The dataset draws on a diverse array of digitised historical cookbooks in over a dozen languages, unified through machine translation and NLP-based entity extraction.

By providing standardised, English-language recipe texts alongside structured metadata and extracted culinary entities, **this dataset enables researchers to study the evolution of European food culture across time and geography**. The dataset has been compiled in compliance with applicable copyright and database right provisions, with careful attention to the legal and ethical dimensions of working with digitised cultural heritage materials.

Future work will focus on expanding the corpus with additional sources, refining the entity extraction through human validation, and developing analytical tools for exploring culinary trends at scale.

Annex I

Dataset files: <https://zenodo.org/records/19328667>

